

**THE IMPACT ON A COMPOSITE PLATE :
THE LAY-UP INFLUENCE (EXPERIMENTS AND MODELISATION)**

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ABSTRACT

The lay-up of carbon reinforced plastic plates has got an influence on the behaviour of such plates under impact loading.

In this paper, we focus on the understanding and modelling of that influence.

- The shape of the delaminated zone is analysed and modeled

- The dependance of the energy absorption on the lay-up is analysed through wave propagation considerations.

INTRODUCTION

The modelling of impact requires the study of an energy balance between the indenter and the target.

The impact of a sphere on a carbon fiber reinforced plastic plate (CFRP) may be considered as an impactor's kinetic energy transfer to the plate. This energy separates into various types of energies, the relative importance of which depends on parameters such as the initial velocity of the indenter.

Let us consider a diagram showing the energy absorbed by the plate versus the initial impact velocity of the impactor for 24 plies-CFRP with various lay-ups.

This diagram can be divided into three separate zones called low, medium and high velocity zones (I, II, III) (Fig. 1). Table 1 summarizes the various energy types that are to be taken into account in the energy balance.

Fig. 1 Velocity zones.

ZONES	I	II	III
Energy types negl. means neglected	-contact (Hertz) -membrane -bending -inertia [1]	-delamination -fiber breaking -elastic (negl.) [2]	-plug-in -friction [3]
Lay-up dependance of abs. en. (Ea)	DEPENDANT		INDEPENDANT
Behaviour	STATIC	DYNAMIC	

Table 1 The energy types.

This paper deals with the influence of the lay-up in zone II (100-200 m/s) showing both experimental and theoretical results. The lay-up influence on the impact behavior of CFRP may be divided into two different phenomena :

- The shape of the delaminated zone
- The energy absorbed by the plate during impact.

THE SHAPE OF THE DELAMINATED ZONE

The delamination caused by the impact of an elastic sphere seems to depend on the lay-up in both zones I and II.

EXPERIMENTS :

As shown by US-SCAN experiments, the shape of delaminated areas has been shown to depend on the lay-up. A correlation has been found between the shape of this area and the flexion moduli in the plane of the plates. We present on figure 2 experimental flexion results, using a visco-elasticimeter at a frequency of 7.5 Hz.

The higher the flexion modulus in a given direction, the more delaminated the plate in that direction.

Fig. 2 Correlation between flexion moduli and delamination.

MODELISATION :

In the frame of non equilibrium Thermodynamics, a variable must be defined that would represent the delamination of the plate at any state of penetration p (fig. 3).

The delamination being anisotropic, a tensorial damage variable noted \underline{A} has been introduced in the following manner.

For a given state of penetration p ($0 < p < 1$)

Fig. 3 Penetration of the plate.

It is assumed that the **I** part of the plate does not delaminate anymore, and that the delamination increment at perforation state p is, thanks to what has been already stated, proportionnal to the flexion moduli of the **S** part of the plate ahead of the impactor.

In other words : $\dot{\underline{A}}(p) = \underline{B}(p) \cdot \dot{A}(p)$

where $\underline{B}(p)$ is the flexion matrix of **S** divided by its trace to provide $0 < A < 1$.

and $A(p) = \int_0^p \dot{A}(p) dp$ is defined as the scalar damage variable.

Hence, $\underline{A}(p) = \int_0^p \underline{B}(p) \cdot \dot{A}(p) dp$.

The delamination length in direction n can then be defined as $D(p, n) = n \cdot \underline{A}(p) \cdot n$

In the complete model developed elsewhere [4], we define the spreading velocity of delamination as a function of penetration p . It is possible to calculate $A(p)$ and $\underline{B}(p)$ at any state p of penetration. The shape of the delaminated, zone considered as a projection through the plane of the plate, can be drawn :

Fig. 4 The delamination.

This modelisation enables us to predict relatively accurately the shape of the delaminated area for any lay-up (Fig. 5). Hypothesis and limits of the model have already been discussed elsewhere [4].

Fig. 5 Comparison calculation / experiments

THE ENERGY ABSORBED BY THE PLATE DURING IMPACT

The second phenomenon we will deal with in this paper, is the energy absorption of the plate during impact. Using the former model, it is possible to predict the speed of the sphere versus time [4]. It gives good results for quasi-isotropic materials. In the case of other lay-ups, the absorbed energy appears to depend on the lay-up, and the residual velocity cannot be predicted by the model. All the experiments were performed using a 1 g steel spherical indenter with an initial velocity of 150 m/s.

HETEROGENEITY EFFECTS :

The energy absorbed by laminates made of twelve 0° and twelve 90° plies in various sequences is shown on Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 Energy absorbed by $(0_{12}, 90_{12})$ laminates.

An optical microscope observation shows that delamination occurs between two plies of different orientation. The volume of the plate affected by delamination is the same for all the lay-ups. Hence the fact that the delaminated surface of $(0,90)_6s$ appears to be bigger than the one of $(0_6,90_6)s$. It is in contradiction with the above observed absorbed energy.

It suggests that another energy absorption mechanism different from delamination has not yet been taken into account.

The propagation of an elastic wave through an interface separating two media, generates up to three reflected and three transmitted waves, and also Stoneley waves propagating at the interface [5] (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 Interaction Wave-(0,90) Interface (slowness surfaces).

But an interface has got an influence on wave propagation only if the thicknesses of the two media are greater than the wave length. Else the two media appear as one homogeneous medium. For a wave length larger than a ply but smaller than a quarter of a plate (i.e. the frequency range is between 4 MHz and 24 MHz), the wave will only be affected by the interface $(0,90)$ of the $(0_6,90_6)s$, thus enhancing reflections, surface waves, delocalizing elastically the impact energy. This phenomenon has been modeled using slowness surfaces formalism (Fig.7)

On the contrary, none of the interfaces of the $(0,90)_6s$ will be seen by the wave.

ANISOTROPY EFFECTS :

The energy absorbed by $(+\Omega,-\Omega)_6s$ laminates under ballistic impact is shown on Fig. 8. In this case, the plate appears homogeneous in its thickness for the considered frequency range.

Fig. 8 Energy absorbed by $(+\Omega,-\Omega)_6s$ laminates.

The wave surfaces of the layered plates have been modeled analytically using a method developed by F. C. Moon [6] (Fig. 9). The outer sheet of the wave surface is related to the quasi-longitudinal vibration and the inner sheet to the quasi-transversal one. It appears that the shape of the outer sheet of the surface is correlated to the energy absorbed by the plate. The outer sheet of the surface is roughly elliptical. The higher the eccentricity of the ellipse, the higher the absorbed energy.

Fig. 9 Wave surfaces of $(+\Omega, -\Omega)_{6s}$ laminates.

CONCLUSION

The lay-up of carbon fiber reinforced plastic plates has got an influence on its behavior under ballistic impact loading at medium velocities. It causes a delamination, the shape of which has been modeled in the frame of non equilibrium thermodynamics. The model enables to predict the final shape of the delamination. But it has been pointed out that delamination is not the only phenomenon responsible for energy absorption. The effect of heterogeneity and anisotropy on wave propagation induces partial reflections, surface waves and energy delocalization that are to be taken into account in the energy balance.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- 1-Shivakumar K. ASME Vol 52 pp 674-680 (1985)
- 2-Beaumont N. Journées spécialisées de l'AMAC (1/1988)
- 3-Avery J.G, Porter T.R. ASTM-STP 568 pp 3-26 (1975)
- 4-Beaumont N., Penazzi L. IV Int. Conf. on Mech. Prop.of Mat. at High Rates of Strain. Oxford(3/89)
- 5-Rokhlin S.I., Bolland T.K., Adler L. J.Acoust.Soc.Am, 79(4), pp 906-918 (1986)
- 6-Moon F.C. J.Compos.Mat, 6, pp 62-79 (1972)

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